

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

REVIEW ON METAL CONJUGATED HERBAL NANOPARTICLES LOADED IN SKIN CREAM

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 20/09/2024

Available online
26/10/2024

Keywords

Metallic Nanoparticles,
Characterization Studies,
Phytochemical Study,
Cream.

ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles gained great importance in drug delivery system to control surface properties particle size and site-specific action of drugs with optimum therapeutic activity and dosage regimen. Nanoparticles found great promise in non-viral gene delivery system. In the new technology which are nano sized particles for delivering drugs in nano pathway, which are used in several applications like diagnostics, preparation of vaccines and therapeutics. Nanoparticles used to treat kidney diseases tuberculosis, CNS disorders, skin diseases and various types of cancers. Different types of nanoparticles are solid-lipid nanoparticles, polymeric nanoparticles, silica nanoparticles, carbon nanomaterials, and dendrimers. In this review the different formulation and synthesis of nanoparticles were explained, focusing on metallic based nanoparticles followed by its characterization studies antimicrobial and antioxidant studies. Phytochemical screening of herbal extract active constituents was explained. The formulation and evaluation nanoparticles followed by preparation of cream as facial cosmetic also included.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr. Nishad KM** et al. Review on Metal Conjugated Herbal Nanoparticles Loaded in Skin Cream. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2024;14(09).

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INTRODUCTION NANO DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Kreuter and Speiser discovered nanoparticles in 1970. Nanoparticles are defined as the nanometric colloidal particle having synthetic and semisynthetic polymers. Diameter of nanoparticles is 10-1000 nm. During 1980's solid core nanoparticle developed as a result of physical stability improvement of liposomes. The drugs are incorporated in the matrix are covered by polymeric sheath.

Nanoparticles gained great importance in drug delivery system to control surface properties particle size and site-specific action of drugs with optimum therapeutic activity and dosage regimen. Nanoparticles found great promise in non-viral gene delivery system.^{1,5} In the recent years, nano drug delivery system has vast importance in the field of targeted drug delivery. In this method nano sized particles with one more than one therapeutically active ingredients are incorporated into the polymeric matrix. They boost the biological activity by minimizing destructive toxic effects. In therapeutics nanotechnology found useful in oncology which consist of polymer coated nano materials or lipid vesicles and imaging probes in nano scale is used in medical imaging or image directed therapy. Because of promising capacity of nanoparticles researchers undergo massive undertakings in the formulation of nanomaterial-based drug delivery system in the research field and in advanced nanoparticle platform.²

ADVANTAGES

Nanoparticles are biodegradable and sterilizable. They are non-toxic and can be stored up to 1 year. Nanoparticles can be formulated as parenteral, oral and nasal formulations. Nanoparticles act as carrier in agricultural and industrial fields. Nanoparticles have least chemical reaction and have higher drug loading capacity which serve as a factor for conserving the drug activity. Alteration in the particle of nanoparticle and their surface characteristics can be made to prolong the active and passive drug target.¹

DISADVANTAGES

Have higher production cost. Possibility of particle aggregation may occur if they have higher surface area. Removal of byproduct is needed. Chances of content leakage and bursting. Liquid and drug form of nanoparticle are difficult to handle. Difficult to deal large-scale production³.

METAL CONJUGATED NANOPARTICLE

Purely metal nanoparticle is made with metal precursor. Nanoparticle exhibit characteristic optoelectrical properties due to localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR). Metal nanoparticle can be conjugated with suitable ligand to enhance their binding property and excellent site-specific action.⁶

Fig.1: Metal Nanoparticle⁴

PROPERTIES

Metal nanoparticle reflex multiple practical application. They expose broad spectrum electromagnetic absorption. They show plasmon excitation and quantum confinement. Metal nanoparticle is a fascinating material that have remarkable properties like large surface energies high thermal and electrical conductivity. Due to metallic sort of character, they possess high melting point, high density, shining and lustrous property.^{1,7}

METHODOLOGY

For this discussion we referred 30 articles. Out of this we omitted 20 articles and 10 articles found beneficial for the purpose. To develop anti acne cream by formulating silver nanoparticles for anti-acne process with the technique of green synthesis, followed by evaluating studies of silver nanoparticle and nano particle loaded aqueous cream. This ongoing process includes plant authentication, plant extraction, synthesis of silver nanoparticles, evaluation of nanoparticles, formulation of cream and evaluation of cream. Silver nanoparticle developed through centrifugation and undergone characterization studies with UV-visible spectrophotometer, SEM, TEM, FTIR, XRD-Xray diffraction studies. The formulated silver nanoparticles were screened for anti-microbial activity and authenticated by exposing them to gram negative bacteria.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Silver nanoparticle was developed through green synthesis. Aqueous extract was taken from the herbal source. The green synthesized silver conjugated nanoparticles were loaded in skin cream. The formulation was then undergone characterization and evaluation study. The effect of the cream for gram negative bacteria was authenticated. The herbal drugs containing active constituents avoids the side effects thereby enhances targeted delivery and patient compliances.

FORMULATION CONCEPT OF NANOPARTICLES

The formulation concept of nanoparticles refers to the design and development of nanoparticle-based systems for various applications, considering their physical, chemical, and biological properties. It includes,

Composition: Selection of materials, such as metals, polymers, lipids, or ceramics.

Size and shape: Control of nanoparticle dimensions to optimize properties.

Stability and storage: Maintenance of nanoparticle integrity during storage and handling.

Toxicity and safety: Evaluation of nanoparticle biocompatibility and potential toxicity.

Targeting and delivery: Design of nanoparticles to reach specific sites of action, such as tumors or organs.³

SYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES

Top-Down Process

It involves breaking of huge particle to develop nanoparticles through physical method.

Bottom-Process

It includes the generation of large nanoparticle by addition of large number of single atoms or molecules.

Fig.2: Synthesis of Nanoparticle³

Physical Method

Metal nanoparticle is developed through evaporation condensation and laser ablation with tube furnace and atmospheric pressure. The brightening advantage of laser ablation method is the generation of pure and uncontaminated silver nanoparticle without using chemical reagents.

Chemical Synthesis

Chemical synthesis involves chemical precursors by altering the chemical composition. Chemical reaction initiated and progressed through utilization of catalyst.

Biological Synthesis

Biological synthesis involves synthesis of nanoparticle from plants, bacteria, fungi. This method is uncomplicated, simplest, nontoxic and ozone friendly.

Fig.3: Synthesis of Nanoparticle⁴

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOPARTICLES

UV-Visible Spectroscopy

UV-visible spectroscopy is a quantitative technique used to measure how much a chemical substance absorbs light. Metal nanoparticles can be identified and characterized. Nanoparticles ranging from 2-10 nm are generally characterized. This is done by measuring the intensity of light that passes through a sample with respect to the intensity of light that passes through a reference sample. The curve of absorbance against wave length is obtained.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

In this high energy electron beam is passed through the surface of the specimen to generate the images. The configuration and chemical profile of nanostructure can be studied and determined.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) offers high resolution and high imaging speed for direct imaging and dimensional measurements of micro and nanostructures. SEMs with moderate electron energies (around 10 keV) provide nanometer resolution and are capable of transmitting particles in nanometer size range.

Transmission Electron Microscopy

It is a technique that images the transition of a beam of electrons through a sample. TEM is a suitable method to estimate the particle size, grain size, morphology and size distribution of nanoparticles. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) typically achieves higher lateral resolution than SEMs due to its high electron energies (above 100 keV). TEM come at significantly higher purchase and operating cost compared to SEM.

Zeta Potential

Zeta potential is the potential difference existing between the surface of a solid particle immersed in the conducting liquid. Stability of the synthesized nanoparticle can be analyzed. More stabilized nanoparticle have high zeta potential.

XRD-Xray Diffraction

XRD is most extensively used for the detection of crystalline structure and phase identification. The XRD gives information of crystal structure, lattice spacing, phase features and crystal size. In X-ray diffraction instrument unique crystalline arrangement exhibit different diffraction characteristics. Phase determination is done by matching unique diffraction profiles isolated from unidentified compound with known crystallographic patterns. The x rays produced are radiated into the sample, it is then reflected from the sample and strikes the detector. This technique is like verifying fingerprint evidence at the crime scene.

FTIR-Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy

The FTIR is commonly used for identification of organic functional group bonded to surface of nanoparticle. The rotation and vibration of molecule affected by infrared radiation at a specific wavelength is monitored by FTIR. This method detect variation in molecular interaction between entities. This technique is required to attain infrared absorption profile of the three states of matter. An FTIR equipment collects concurrent and detailed spectral information across the broad wavelength region. This provides a substantial merit across a spectroscopic disperser, which have spectral analysis at narrow bandwidth. FTIR quantifies the vibrational frequency of the entity that gets stimulated by the infrared energy. FTIR method has several advantages that identifies and examine unrecognized elements, it analyses the extend of impurities in the sample and also it identifies the leached additives.^{8,9}

Fig.4: Characterization of Nanoparticle⁵

EVALUATION OF NANOPARTICLES

Particle Size

The size of the particle is determined using Malvern zetasizer, photon correlation spectroscopy. Based on the type of polymer used particle size may vary. 350-600nm range is used for determination of particle size with scanning electron microscope.

Percentage of drug entrapment

Suspension of prepared nanoparticle were centrifuged for 30 minutes at 2000 rpm. Collect the supernatant and particles wash with water for conduct another centrifugation process. The UV-visible spectroscopy is used to determine presence of free drug in supernatant.

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency percentage} = \frac{(\text{Amount of drug added} - \text{Amount of free drug})}{\text{Amount of drug added}} \times 100$$

Atomic Force Microscopy Studies

Surface morphology of drug loaded nanoparticle can be characterized using atomic force microscopy [AFM] studies. Using milli-Q water, suspension of nanoparticle was prepared and kept on a clean glass surface for overnight drying. The observation analyzed using AFM using silicon probes. To prevent the surface damage the measurement is analyzed using intermittent contact mode.

In-Vitro Release of Nanoparticle by Simple Diffusion Cell

With simple diffusion cell apparatus in vitro release was performed. Freshly developed phosphate buffer having pH 7.4 is used for dissolution medium. To the dissolution medium the sigma membrane is soaked. With magnetic stirrer the medium is stirred by maintaining the temperature at 37°C to 0.5°C. 5 mL of sample is taken periodically to analyze spectrophotometrically.¹⁰

Antimicrobial activity

Antimicrobial action of formulation integrated with metal nanoparticles is potent against disease-causing gram-negative bacteria like *P. Aeruginosa*, *C. albicans*, *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris* etc. Nanoparticles combined with suitable metal containing dosage forms substantially minimize the colony formation of entire panel of pathogens.¹¹

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles shows broad spectrum antibacterial activity against bacteria like gram negative and gram positive.

Mechanisms of existing antibiotic resistance can be overcome in majority of nanoparticles and can also overcome not less than one of familiar resistance mechanisms hint at 'Antibacterial activity of nanoparticles' division (it involves the bacterial membrane distribution and barrier of biofilm development). These reactions are outcome of bacterial system of nanoparticles, it is on the basis of their specific physicochemical effects.

Fighting microorganisms using several mechanisms.

The antimicrobial action of conventional antibiotics is generally simple, which is partially why bacterial aversion has appeared. In variation to conventional antibiotics, nanoparticles fighting microbes via several mechanism are concurrently active. Performing as a good transporter of antibiotics. NPs not only can fight microbial and bacterial resistance, but also behave as a carrier and medium of antibiotics.

Application of NPs in antibacterial properties.

The antibacterial covering of imbedded devices contains two forms of human imbedded devices with antibacterial covering; First one is fully imbedded device, like dental implants or heart valve. The antimicrobial covering of cardiovascular equipment in specific must have suitable blood compatibility to avoid thrombosis. The usage of titanium oxide covering on implants is the basis of pore morphology with phosphorus, silicon, calcium and silver particle enrichment.¹²

INTRODUCTION OF MEDICINAL PLANT TO NANO FORMULATION

For numerous centuries, the utilization of herbal remedies has constituted a fundamental aspect in the therapeutic management of infectious maladies, thereby presenting a plausible alternative to traditional medicinal practices. Nonetheless, the constrained bioavailability and solubility associated with these remedies have posed substantial obstacles to their broad-based application. Fortunately, the advent of nanoparticles derived from plant sources has instigated a paradigm shift within this domain, markedly improving both the bioavailability and solubility characteristics of herbal therapeutic agents. The interplay between herbal medicine and nanotechnology has garnered significant scholarly interest in contemporaneous discourse, largely propelled by advancements within the sphere of nanotechnology.

Nanoparticles have emerged as a preeminent system for drug delivery, and the integration of these structures with herbal medicines has been extensively celebrated as a transformative innovation. By capitalizing on nanostructured methodologies, it becomes possible to refine herbal extracts to enhance therapeutic efficacy while concurrently reducing required dosages and mitigating adverse repercussions. Additionally, the implementation of biosynthesized nanoparticles, derived from carbon dioxide via eco-friendly processes, emerges as an appealing solution, rendering this modality an enticing option for the pursuit of sustainable health care practices.¹³

EXTRACTION TECHNIQUES**Decoction:**

Here a specific quantity of crude drug is boiled with a specific volume of water for a specific time and after that the solution is filtered to receive the solid which is separated after cooling in order to obtain the water soluble and thermostable principles. In decoction technique the extract consists of huge number of hydrophilic impurities. The volatile and thermolabile substance cannot be extracted by decoction technique.

Maceration:

Originally this process would use crude drug in a whole form or powders and would mean placing the drug in a solvent which contains warm water at a room temperature for several days with occasional stirring to ensure solubilization of the drug. It is then filtered and pressed to give a product ready for use as extract, of the product formed. This is simple technique for extraction process. In which long-time extraction and less extraction efficiency is considered as disadvantage.

Percolation:

Percolation refers to a method of plant extractive that is usually all inclusive and thorough since soluble components are extracted from the plant material in a step-wise manner with the aid of a fresh solvent. In this method, a solvent is passed over a non-moving plant material for an extended period of time, so that a large amount of target phytochemicals can be extracted from the plant efficiently and completely. Percolation is most effective extraction techniques than maceration method, and as this is a continuous process here fresh solvent is always replaced instead of saturated solvent.^{14,15}

Soxhlet extraction:

Soxhlet extraction method uses Soxhlet extractor whereby a solvent is heated to evaporate the liquid and the evaporated liquid rises when passing through a condenser it is allowed to drop on the crude drug that contains the required compounds for extraction this type of extraction is continuous in circles.¹⁴

Counter current Extraction:

In this method, wet ground raw material is subjected to processing on toothed disc disintegrators to form a simple slurry. The compound flows in one direction where it is extracted with the solvent in a cylindrical extractor. As the starting material moves further concentrated extract is released at one side of the extractor, while the dry material (marc) is released from the other end and that is the opposite side of the extractor.¹⁴

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Test for Proteins

Millon's test: Crude extract was mixed with 2ml Millon's reagent, white precipitate formed which become red on heating which indicate the occurrence of protein.

Ninhydrin test: Crude extract was boiled with 2ml of 0.2% solution of Ninhydrin, violet colour indicates amino acids and proteins.

Test for Carbohydrates

Fehling's test: Mixequal volume of Fehling A and Fehling B reagents and mixed together with 2ml of crude extract and boiled. Appearance of brick red precipitate at the base of the test tube indicates the reducing sugars.

Benedict's test: 2ml of Benedict's reagent is mixed with crude extract and boiled, formation of reddish-brown precipitate indicates carbohydrates.

Molisch's test: 2ml of Molisch's reagent mixed with crude extract and shaken properly. Then 2ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was poured besides the test tube. Violet ring formed at the interphase indicates carbohydrate.

Iodine test: 2ml of iodine solution mixed with crude extract. Formation of purple or dark blue colour indicates carbohydrate.

Test for Phenols and Tannins

2% of 2ml FeCl₃ solution mixed with crude extract. Black or blue-green indicates phenols and tannins.

Test for Flavonoids

Shinoda test: Few pieces of magnesium ribbon mixed with crude extract and drop wisely add concentrated HCl. Appearance of pink scarlet colour after few minutes indicates the flavonoids.

Test for Saponins

5ml distilled water mixed with crude extract and shaken vigorously. Formation of stable foam indicates saponins.

Test for Glycosides

Liebermann's test: The mixture of 2ml of chloroform and acetic acid is added to the crude extract. Allow to cool in ice. Concentrated H₂SO₄ added carefully. Violet to blue to green indicates the steroidal nucleus (glycone)

Keller- Killani test: Add 2ml of glacial acetic acid containing 1-2 drops of 2% solution of FeCl₃ in to the crude extract. The mixture was then poured into another test tube containing 2ml of concentrated H₂SO₄. A brown ring at the interphase indicates cardiac glycosides.

Test for Alkaloids 2ml of 1% HCl mixed with crude extract and heated gently. Mayer's And Wagner's reagents added. Turbidity of precipitate indicates alkaloids.

Fig.5: Phytochemical Screening¹⁶

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF EXTRACT

Anti-inflammatory Activity-Plant extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory activity, and reduce symptoms of various diseases. Plant extracts of turmeric, boswellia and ginger treat inflammatory condition. The presence of active components like polyphenols, terpenoids, flavonoids and the plant extracts show the anti-inflammatory activity.

Anti diabetic Activity -Plant extracts exhibit anti-diabetic activity; it helps to control the blood sugar level and management of diabetes. The plant extracts of cinnamon, bitter melon, fenugreek treat diabetes. The presence of active components like alkaloids, phenolic acids, glycosides, the plant extracts possess the anti-diabetic activity.

Anti-cancer Activity -Plant extracts exhibit anti-cancer activity; it assists in treatment/prevention of different types of cancer. Plant extracts of turmeric, ginger and green tea shows pro-apoptotic and anti-proliferative effect in cancer cells. In presence of polyphenols, glycosides and alkaloids helps in anticancer activity.

Antimicrobial Activity- Plant extracts exhibit antimicrobial activity, helps in killing or reducing the growth of microorganisms like virus, fungi and bacteria. The plant extracts of eucalyptus, rosemary and tea exhibit antimicrobial activity, due to the presence of compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids and essential oils.

Antioxidant Activity- Plant extracts exhibit antioxidant activity and assist in decreasing the possibility of chronic diseases. Plant extracts of pomegranate, grapes seed and green tea have higher antioxidant activity, due to the presence of components like carotenoids, flavonoids and polyphenols.¹⁷

CREAMS

Creams are semisolid emulsions, either water-in-oil or oil-in- water. The consistency of dosage form varies between water and oil creams, which are mostly used for cosmetic purposes including cleansing, improving appearances, beautifying, and providing protective and therapeutic functions. Creams are topical preparations used for the localized effect of drug delivery into the skin or mucous membrane.¹⁸

TYPES OF CREAMS

Oil in water (O/W) Creams - Creams are primarily composed of oil droplets dispersed in a continuous aqueous phase. In this emulsion, the oil is dispersed throughout the aqueous phase as droplets, they are termed as oil in water.

Water in oil (W/O) Creams - Creams are primarily composed of water droplets dispersed in a continuous oil phase. When the water is dispersed throughout the oil phase as droplets, they are termed as water in oil emulsion.

Classification of creams

- 1)Based on the function: e.g.) cleansing, foundation, massage
- 2)Based on the characteristic properties: e.g.) Cold cream, vanishing cream
- 3)Based on the nature or type of emulsion^{17,19,20}

FORMULATION OF CREAMS

Water:

Water is the most versatile and essential raw material in cream formulation. In skin creams purified water serve as a solvent, effectively dissolving and blending other ingredients to create a homogenous mixture, while its purity ensures the absence of toxins, microorganism and pollutants.

Oils, Fats, Waxes:

Oils, fats, waxes and any ingredients replaced or derived from them are active in cracking formulations of creams enhancing moisture absorbing/land retention properties of creams and or their constituents. Cream heating and whipping incorporates simethicone as an oil phase. Cream base contains oils for scents and moisture. Waxes can function as emollients, fats are mostly utilized in creams in order to provide thickening action and oil is from a different angle because it acts as perfume, bactericides, and used for water-retaining purposes. Examples: Oils- olive oil, coconut oil, liquid paraffin, Fats- Lanolin, Waxes- Beeswax, carnauba waxes.

Colorants:

Coloring agents are added mainly to improve the appearance of the product. Colors developed in laboratories are found to have higher stability with greater intensity.

Example: sunset yellow, eosin, Amaranth, Titanium dioxide, Cochineal

Buffers:

Buffers are employed in order to maintain the pH level of the cream formulation.

Example: Phosphate buffer, Hydrochloric acid, Phosphoric acid

Preservative:

Preservative is used in order to improve the shelf life and to control microbial growth. Preservatives are used to protect the cream from contamination during formulation, storage, shipment. It inhibits the growth of microorganism that alter the properties of formulation.

Example: Parabens, Phenolic

Antioxidants:

One of the ways to improve the stability of such formulation is the use of anti-oxidants which protects the formulation from oxidative degradation. Since most of the formulations are aqueous in nature, anti-oxidants in aqueous form are used. Antioxidants helps to prevent alteration due to oxygen exposure.

Example: Sodium metabisulphite, Sodium formaldehyde.

Humectants:

In majority of skin care preparation humectants are essential multifunctional component. They are hygroscopic in nature. They have different properties like exfoliation, moisturization etc.

Example: Betaine, Glycerin, Hydroxyethyl urea, Propylene Glycol

Emollients:

These are generally referred as moisturizers. It provides moisturization effect and protect skin from drying. It is used to treat dryness of skin. It enhances the skin ability to withhold water, preventing the water loss from the skin by delivering an oil layer. Emollients also provide lubrication action to the skin.²¹

PREPARATION OF CREAMS**Trituration:**

In this method finely divided insoluble powders are generally mixed through geometric dilution by making a well and gentle blending. Mortar and pestle are used to eliminate air pocket formation.

Levigation:

In this process coarse particle are added into mixtures to produce a uniform mixture. This is also called as wet grinding. It involves mixing of coarse powder with base in rubber motion.

Fusion method:

This method is employed when active ingredients are miscible by ointment bases. The soluble ingredients are added after melting the base. To receive a smooth texture the mixture is thoroughly triturated.²¹

EVALUATION OF CREAMS**Determination of p^H:**

Measuring the pH of the cream can be done at room temperature using a standard digital pH meter. This involves diluting an appropriate amount of the formulation in a suitable solvent and placing it in a beaker.

Physical Appearance:

To determine the physical properties of the cream by examining its color, texture, and consistency.

Spreadability:

The sample of cream was placed between two glass slide and weight is applied for 5 minutes on the slide. The time taken for the upper slide to move across the lower slide was used to measure spreadability. $S = m(l/t)$ m = weight applied on upper slide, l = length moved on the glass slide, t = time taken

Homogeneity:

The formulated cream assessed for homogeneity based on its visual appearance, tactile feel

Viscosity:

The viscosity of cream can be measured using Brookfield viscometer.

Dye test:

To determine the type of cream (O/W or W/O), mix the scarlet dye with the cream. Then drop of cream is placed on a slide and covered with a cover slip and observe under a microscope. If disperse globule shows red and ground colorless, it indicates an o/w type cream. conversely, if the reverse condition is obtained it signifies a w/o type of cream

Irritancy test:

Mark a 1sq cm on the back of the left hand. Apply the cream to specified area and note the time. Check for irritancy, erythema, oedema at regular intervals up to 24 hours and report any observed reactions.

Accelerated stability study:

Accelerated stability studies are carried out for the formulation following the ICH guidelines.²¹

CONCLUSION

Nano drug delivery system is an advanced controlled drug delivery system in various diseases, especially in anti-cancer treatment. Metallic nanoparticles are well advanced and more stable materials. The drug entrapment efficiency is more. The synthesized nanoparticle can be characterized by characterization studies and the anti-microbial efficiency or biological activity can be determined. The herbal drugs containing active constituents avoids the side effects there by improves the patient safety. The phytochemical screening of herbal extract assures the presence of active medicament. The formulated and evaluated nanoparticles can be loaded on creams for the easy of application also to improve the patient compliance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We wish to express our sincere graduate to the authors of the review article and the institute.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATION

CNS	-Central Nervous System
LSPR	-Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance
SEM	-Scanning Electron Microscopy
TEM	-Transmission Electron Microscopy
XRD	-Xray Diffraction
FTIR	-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
AFM	-Atomic Force Microscopy
NP	-Nanoparticles

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